

A Survey on File Carving Process Using Foremost and Scalpel

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Abstract— The development of digital memory devices follows the rapid development of computers. Data loss is a prevalent issue with digital memory. Using file carving techniques, for example, the problem of knowledge loss might be remedied. Carving tools like the scalpel and Foremost might be used to conduct file carving techniques. The scalpel is now working, and depending on how much disc space you're trying to scan and recover, recovering your deleted file will take some time. Foremost is a command-line utility for recovering files from a variety of file systems, including fat, ext3, and others. Unfortunately, the filenames supplied by both tools are not the same as the original filenames, and duplicate carved files may exist in some circumstances because many files are fragmented and appear to be independent files. This study is being conducted to better understand and compare the performance of the Scalpel and Foremost carving processes based on three parameters: the number of return files, file validation, and process rate.

Keywords: File Carving, Data Recovery, Digital Forensics

I. INTRODUCTION

Computer files can be recovered from raw data regardless of the type of file system, and file retrieval is achievable even if the file system information has been totally obliterated, making file carving a very strong approach. As a result, the approach provides additional data recovery ways to supplement digital inquiry where typical data recovery procedures are insufficient or have failed. When retrieving data and files that have been previously erased, extracting files from the unallocated space of a digital data storage device, and in circumstances where a storage device or a file system has been damaged or corrupted, file carving comes in handy.

Digital forensics investigators now have access to a wide range of commercial and open source digital forensics tools. The purpose of these tools is to provide layers of abstraction that allow investigators to copy digital evidence properly and conduct routine investigations without becoming overwhelmed by low-level considerations like physical disc management. A file carver is one of the most critical tools in a digital forensics investigator's toolbox. File carvers search one or more target disc images for occurrences of headers and footers, which are strings of bytes at predictable offsets, from databases of headers and footers.

The purpose is to "carve" sequences of bytes into conventional files by identifying the beginning and ending

locations of files in disc images. Additional file-type-specific rules may apply, such as determining whether the footer is closest to a discovered header or farthest away from the header, or if the footer is included or excluded in the carved file. This paper discusses the file carving process analysis of scalpel and foremost based on some parameters.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION

For scholars and practitioners alike, digital forensics is a relatively new profession that brings various obstacles. Unfortunately, contemporary forensic research has little or no influence because many researchers are unfamiliar with real-world digital forensic difficulties and the practical limits that investigators face. The solution is to perform investigator-centric research with the goal of producing discoveries that are valuable in the real world, bridging the gap between academic research and the necessary real-world inquiry tools and methodologies. Furthermore, the size and complexity of the targets of investigations is growing. Practitioners require accurate results in order to accurately pick the appropriate tool for a given circumstance, reducing total case processing time while ensuring investigative integrity. File carving is a challenging and intricate procedure that is made even more difficult by the wide range of instruments available. Many forensic investigators are unaware of the various file cutting tools' capabilities and/or limits. Despite targeted active research, the professional digital forensic investigator or data recovery practitioner nevertheless faces a number of challenges: which file cutting tools are the most effective in terms of;

- 1) the percentage of files that were successfully retrieved
- 2) the accuracy and dependability of the tool's output
- 3) the tool's processing speed

III. FILE CARVING STRATEGIES

File carving necessitates one or more complete passes over each image in the absence of metadata providing a complete description of the contents of a set of disc images. Because a file header can reside anywhere in a disc image, T_{read} , the total number of bytes required to read a disc image once is a performance limiting factor. For all carving strategies, T_{read} is constant and cannot be significantly lowered through intelligent optimization. Other elements that influence the

minimal cost include the time it takes to look for headers, footers, and necessary strings, memory-to-memory copy operations, and the total number of bytes written for carved files, T_{write} . A few guiding concepts are appropriate to maximize the performance of a file carving application. Most are standard programming "sense," but because of the massive volumes of data these applications must transport, they are critical in file carving. The following principles were compiled after reviewing existing open source file carvers and designing Scalpel and Foremost:

- A. A. Once the data has been read from the disc image, the amount of time spent looking for headers and footers should be minimized. This entails using a fast string search algorithm and reducing the number of needless searches (for example, not searching for footers for which no viable header has been found).
- B. Memory-to-memory copying should be kept to a bare minimum. Billions (and soon trillions) of bytes of data are copied by file carvers. Despite the fact that disc operations are orders of magnitude slower than memory copies, too many memory-to-memory copies degrade performance. Data should be written directly to carved files from the buffer used for reads against the disc image if at all possible. These are some of the takeaways from the development of high-performance operating systems.
- C. T_{write} should be kept to a minimum by cutting as few files as possible that match the investigator's requirements. Because write operations on mechanical discs are expensive, only those blocks of data in the disc image that fit the file carver's search parameters should be written. This rules out a strategy in which carving processes start anytime a footer is found, but the carved "file" is discarded if no acceptable footer is found.

If these principles are followed, a file carver's performance will be greatly influenced by the number of passes (even partial ones) made over each disc image. To put it another way, the amount of bytes read to complete the carving must be kept as low as possible. Tread's multiplication factor must be as low as feasible. A secondary point is that, all else being equal, sequential passes over the disc image will almost certainly be faster than multiple randomly ordered reads, for two reasons. To begin with, current filesystems conduct block read-ahead, which is disrupted by non-sequential reads. Second, the total amount of time spent searching is minimized.

IV. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SCALPEL AND FOREMOST

Scalpel's bottom constraint on the number of bytes read is T_{read} , which corresponds to one traverse across the disc image without discovering any headers. Because there is nothing to carve in this scenario, the second pass is completely unnecessary. Scalpel's read performance is $2 * T_{read}$ in the worst situation, corresponding to a second iteration that

involves each 10MB chunk in at least one file carving operation. Scalpel reduces T_{write} by only writing carved files if the associated data satisfies all of the constraints set forth in the configuration file for that file type. Even for enormous carve sets, the work queues employed by Scalpel use a modest amount of memory. As a result, it works well on PCs with limited RAM and no swap space..

To process a disc image, Foremost reads $k * T_{read}$ bytes, where $k \geq 1$. Foremost makes additional reads in addition to a single trip over the disc image, which costs T_{read} . The number of reads depends on the number of headers identified and the frequency of whole files to be carved appearing totally in the current chunk of the disc image. It's difficult to get an analytical derivation of k , but some experimental data achieved by instrumenting a copy of Foremost 0.69 give some light. The factor k varied between 1 (for carving an empty disc image) and 45 in the studies described in the next section. This means that the quantity of data read by Foremost is similar to tens of passes over the disc image in some situations, and $45 * T_{read}$ bytes in the worst scenario recorded in the trials. Because many of the readings performed by Foremost overlap, the performance difference between Foremost 0.69 and Scalpel is usually simply a minor constant factor and not on the order of $k / 2$ (because Scalpel performs exactly two passes in the worst case). The filesystem cache is usually used to serve these reads, which reduces but does not eliminate their cost. However, Foremost's performance diminishes when maximum carving sizes are huge. Because many of the reads are non-sequential, they may cause read-ahead issues at the operating system level. Foremost demands a significant amount of memory. At the point of each header discovery, a `malloc()` call allocates a block of dynamic memory equal to the maximum carving size for any file type provided in the configuration file. This indicates that Foremost 0.69 is unable to carve a file larger than the virtual RAM available at the time of header discovery. While this isn't a problem for workstations with a lot of RAM, it can be a pain if you're carving very huge files. At the instant of header discovery, there is also a huge memory-to-memory copy. Unfortunately, Foremost's high memory needs prevent it from carving even moderately huge files on machines lacking swap space. No extensive performance research for 1.0beta was undertaken because this beta version of Foremost appears to be a complete rebuild and does not yet perform all file carving operations correctly in some limited tests.

V. CONCLUSION

Finally, this study looked into the performance of two-file carving tools. There is no such thing as a one-size-fits-all answer when it comes to file carving. The most significant parts of boosting both the number of files recovered and the dependability of tool output are knowledgeable selection of the suitable tool for a certain task and understanding of tool setup. Furthermore, the findings emphasize the ongoing problem of reconstructing file fragments as well as its limitations. This research has also resulted in the compilation of a number of tools that can be used to promote and develop future research. The performance of file carving tools could

be substantially improved in the future thanks to advancements in techniques and tools based on academic study. Using complex data abstractions to hold file carving metadata, improving file validation approaches, and automating post-processing of carving output can all help to improve file carving file speed. In order to help the carving process, more research is needed to reverse-engineer new file types. File carving, on the other hand, is still a useful technique for recovering data and retrieving potential evidence for digital investigations.

REFERENCES

- [1] WinHex 12.1, available at <http://www.winhex.com>
- [2] Forensic Toolkit (FTK), available at <http://www.accessdata.com>.
- [3] V. Roussev, G. G. Richard III, "Breaking the Performance Wall: The Case for Distributed Digital Forensics," Proceedings of the 2004 Digital Forensics Research Workshop (DFRWS 2004), Baltimore, MD.
- [4] Knoppix: A Live Linux CD based on Debian GNU/Linux, available at <http://www.knoppix.net>.
- [5] K. Shanmugasundaram, "Automated Reassembly of Fragmented Images," Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing, 2003.
- [6] Foremost 0.69/1.0beta, available at <http://foremost.sourceforge.net/>
- [7] B. Carrier, "Open Source Digital Forensics Tools: The Legal Argument," @stake Research Report.
- [8] E. Kenneally, "Gatekeeping Out of the Box: Open Source Software as a Mechanism to Assess Reliability for Digital Evidence," Virginia Journal of Law and Technology 13 (2001).
- [9] Knoppix Security Tools Distribution (STD), <http://www.knoppix-std.org/>.
- [10] Helix Live CD, <http://www.e-fense.com/helix/>.